

Preliminary Study on 3GPP Rel-16 and Beyond

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Executive Summary

3GPP plans to release its first version of 5G specification (Rel-15) on June in 2018. As the initial 5G specification, there is still a big gap between Rel-15 and the requirements of IMT-2020 on the performance and supported scenarios. This white paper captured proposals on standardization of 3GPP Rel-16 and beyond from industry, universities and research institutes in 2017. These proposals can be categorized into four aspects as following:

- 1) Proposals on enhancement of key capabilities:
 - a) Spectrum efficiency: D2D assisted MU-MIMO, H-CP OFDM
 - b) Network energy efficiency: Wake-up signalling based power saving, Peak cancelled Multiple-carrier waveform
 - c) Mobility: High speed train solution.
- 2) Supporting mMTC scenario
 - a) r-OFDM
- 3) New features
 - a) NR based positioning
 - b) NOMA
- 4) Efficient network management:
 - a) Wireless Big Data Driven Intelligent RAN Architecture

It is expected that some convergence or agreements can be achieved before the start of Rel-16 to promote the efficiency of standardization procedure and the quality of specification. This white paper will provide important reference for organizations who are 3GPP members already. Input to this white paper is also a good chance for the organizations who are not 3GPP member yet to take part in the 3GPP 5G standardization progress.

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1. Introduction

In Jun 2015, ITU named 5G as “IMI-2020” and published “IMT Vision – Framework and overall objectives of the future development of IMT for 2020 and beyond” , in which the usage scenarios, technical requirements and key performance indicators (KPIs) were identified for 5G [1].

IMT-2020 and beyond are envisaged to expand and support diverse usage scenarios and applications. Three typical usage scenarios are identified for IMT-2020 beyond: Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra-reliable and low latency communications (URLLC), and massive machine type communications (mMTC). The first usage scenario addressed the human-centric use cases and applications. While the last two usage scenarios focus on IoT-centric services. Tightly coupled with the intended usage scenarios and applications for IMT-2020, a broad variety of capabilities are also discussed. Eight key capabilities and their corresponding target values are envisioned. In Table 1-1, eight key capabilities of IMT-2020 are shown, compared with those of IMT- Advanced (IMT-A) [1].

Table1-1 Key capabilities of IMT-2020 (also known as 5G) and 4G

KPIs	Area Traffic capacity	Network Energy Efficiency	Connection Density	Latency (Over the air)	Mobility	User Experience data rate	Peak data rate	Spectral Efficiency
IMT-2020	10Tbps/Km ²	100x	1M/Km ²	1ms	500km/h	100Mbps	10[20] Gbps	3x
IMT-Advanced	0.1Tbps/Km ²	1x	0.1M/Km ²	10ms	350km/h	10Mbps	1Gbps	1x

It is obvious that different usage scenarios along with the current and future trends will result in a great diversity/variety of requirements, i.e. not all key capabilities are same important for all use cases. The relevance of certain key capabilities may be significantly different, depending on the use cases/scenarios, as illustrated in figure1.1.

Figure1.1. The importance of key capabilities in different usage scenarios

3GPP is an international standardization organization with the world-wide members. It has contributed 2G, 3G and 4G international telecommunication standard and served billions of population. 3GPP launched its 5G standardization work from September in 2015. The first step was a study phase in Rel-14 which focused on 5G scenarios and requirements. The second phase started from March in 2017, and the purpose is going to finish the first 5G specification version i.e. Rel-15 on June in 2018. However, as the initial 5G specification, there is still a big gap between Rel-15 and IMT-2020 requirements.

In order to finish the first 5G specification on time, the mMTC scenario was deprioritized by 3GPP RAN plenary, i.e. Rel-15 only considers supporting eMBB and URLLC. As one of three scenarios defined by IMT-2020, mMTC will be absent in Rel-15 and delay to future release.

Regarding the key capabilities, only some of them were focused on in Rel-15, such as latency, spectral efficiency and peak rate, the others got little attention. And it is still uncertain whether latency, spectral efficiency and peak rate can meet IMT-2020 metrics. So it is necessary to continue to take account of improving IMT-2020 key capabilities in Rel-16 and beyond.

In addition to scenarios and key capabilities, new features are needed to support various applications to satisfy user's diverse requirements. On the other hand, the flexible and scalable requirement of 5G system is challenging traditional network operation and maintain, and how to perform network management more efficiently is becoming urgent. 3GPP plans to start the Rel-16 effort on June in 2018 to support all IMT-2020 scenarios and meet all key capabilities. Then Rel-16 and beyond will be submitted to ITU as the 5G candidate technology. This paper captured proposals on standardization of Rel-16 and beyond from industry and academia in 2017. These proposals can be categorized into following aspect:

- 1) Improvement to IMT-2020 key capabilities;
- 2) Support of mMTC scenario;
- 3) New Features;
- 4) Efficient network management.

Each proposal includes three sections, i.e. justification, possible solutions and objective. The justification part explains why this feature/work is needed, such as background, issues solved, benefits etc. The possible solutions part describes the potential solutions for issues mentioned in justification. The objective part gives goals which are supposed to be achieved in standardization for this work/feature, such as expected output, investigation methodology and potential impact to standardization and specification.

2. Improvement to the IMT-2020 key capabilities

Several proposals are raised in this chapter to further improve IMT-2020 key capabilities. The wake-up signal based power saving and peak cancelled multicarrier waveform try to promote the network energy efficiency. The D2D Assisted MU-MIMO precoding and hybrid CP OFDM hope to increase spectrum efficiency further. The high speed train solution studies how to approach or meet the mobility metric raised by IMT-2020.

2.1 Wake-up signal based power saving

2.1.1. Justification

The power consumptions related to DL control channel were analyzed in 3GPP. In LTE, UE is required to decode the PDCCH/EPDCCH to check for its grant when it is not in sleeping mode. Only small percentage of PDCCH/EPDCCH decoding has the results of positive confirmation of DL/UL grant. It is observed that legacy connected mode DRX design and typical parameter settings result in large percentage of power spent in the active state but decoding PDCCH only without any grant in LTE system. Thus, efficient network access scheme with effectively DL control channel monitoring would minimize UE's power consumption. The efficient network access also applies to the paging strategy for IDLE/inactive mode UEs.

It is proposed to perform the wake-up signal design in supporting on-demand access for efficient access to NR system design for UE power saving.

2.1.2. Possible solutions

Current device power saving feature for UE in IDLE and inactive state is for the network to configure the device with the DRX cycle for UE in the sleeping mode. The device wakes up when there is data to transmit. If no data to transmit, the device wakes up periodically and listens to paging or decodes the DL control channel for potential scheduling grant. Most of time, the DL control channel decoding does not have the results of any DL/UL grant. The configured DRX length has the trade-off between the amount of energy saving and latency. If the DRX length is long, the UE will have less energy consumption but high latency in average for the network access. The most energy efficiency mechanism is the on-demand wakeup by the network. The device would stay in sleeping mode and will only wake up when the device has data to send or to receive without periodic wakeup.

An example of the on-demand access is the RFID type of electrical toll collection (ETC) system for collecting the toll of vehicles travelling on the toll road. The ETC device on the vehicle is a passive device. It receives the query signals from transmitter in the toll booth and retransmits the responses with the vehicle identification without any power supply. The backscattering technology is used to trigger the UE to wake up in the sleeping mode without any power supply from the UE. The backscattering technology is for UE having a highly reactive RF front end to stimulate the electromagnetic wave of the received signals from the NR NB. The RF power is converted into DC power through a voltage rectifier. The DC voltage is then able to power the control logic of on-demand access trigger as shown in figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1. RF front end with backscattering technology for on-demand access

The control logic of on-demand access could be designed in the following,

- › Energy detector - If the control logic is an energy detector, the device will trigger the on-demand access when the detected received energy exceeds the threshold. The transmitted signal from the NR NB could be a narrow band beacon. The narrow band beacon would provide high energy concentration for extended coverage. The control logic with energy detector would be detected by all IDLE UEs in the IDLE/inactive mode. This is good for broadcast type of on-demand access but not UE-specific on-demand access. In order to support UE specific on-demand access, multi-beacon backscattering technology is considered. The control logic of multi-beacon backscattering technology is to have one control logic subunit to associate with each beacon. The NR NB will transmit multiple beacons. Each beacon is in different frequency sub-band. Multiple beacons could be transmitted from the NR NB in the same time interval or different time interval. An IDLE/inactive mode UE is configured by the NR NB with the selected combination of the beacons. The IDLE/inactive mode UE will tune to the energy detector to those sub-band of the configured beacons. The control logic will wake up the UE if and only if the energy detection detects the combination of the beacons. For example, 10 beacons are transmitted by the NR NB. If the control logic is designed to receive one distinct beacon, the system will support up to 10 IDLE/inactive mode UEs. If the control logic is designed to receive the combination of 2 distinct beacons out of 10 beacons, the NR system could support up to 45 IDLE/inactive mode UEs. For the combination of 3 distinct beacons, the NR system could support 120 IDLE/inactive mode UEs. The energy detection with multi-beacon backscattering could support UE-specific on-demand access with the control logic detecting the energy from the exact combination of beacons.
- › Controller function and state machine – The control logic with controller function and state machine would have the capability of demodulating the received signals. The control logic would need to demodulate the waveform and decode the contents of the received signals. The contents of the received signals should be simple and straight forward to avoid complicated control logic function with excessive power consumption. A simple 8-digit or 16-digit UE IDs or temperate ID could be used as the control logic. The UE demodulate and decode the received signal and compare with store ID in the state machine to determine whether to wake up or not.

2.1.3. Objective

1) Expect output for this work/feature.

It is expected to output the on-demand network access for IDLE mode and CONNECTED mode UEs in the inactive state in the NR system design. The NR system expects to support high density of UEs/devices within an area with large

number of connectivity. The on-demand access would allow UEs to be in sleeping mode and wake up when there is access on-demand. The backscattering technology take electromagnetic waves of the receive signals and converts to the DC power to trigger the device wakeup without any power supply from the device itself.

2)Investigation methodology.

To evaluate wakeup signal performance, including receiver sensitivity – identify the required energy received to trigger wake up mechanism at UE receiver, passive circuit feasibility – compute the energy accumulation of back scattering technology, low power circuit feasibility – compute the energy required for the wakeup signal detection and power consumption in the detection, link budget – identify the coverage area based on a given Tx power and receiver sensitivity, and Tx power and PSD would be used for wakeup signal design.

3)Potential impact to specification.

Wakeup system design includes wakeup signals design and physical channel design. Wakeup signals will be narrow band signals and waveform with high transmitted power. Physical channel structure includes both inband wakeup channel and out-of-band channel. For inband wakeup channel, NR system have a specific physical channel (s) to transmit the wakeup signals and waveform does not need to be compatible with NR waveform, and it's similar to NR-PSS/SSS with embedded physical channel. For out-of-band physical channel, wakeup physical channel is not part of data carrier, and it could be designed universally for all systems, such as NR, LTE, NB IoT, eMTC.

2.2 Peak Cancelled Multicarrier Waveform

2.2.1. Justification

Orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) is an attractive technique for achieving high speed transmission over frequency-selective channels. So it is widely considered in wireless access in vehicular environments such as 5G, 802.11p, which has been adopted for automotive IT to support V2V networking.

However, one of main limitations in 5G is the high peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) of the transmitted OFDM signals. The large peaks will occasionally reach the amplifier saturation region and therefore result in signal distortion, which causes bit-error-rate (BER) degradation.

To alleviate this problem, a number of PAPR reduction techniques have been introduced in current literature such as in [5]. In general, there are two classes of techniques as pre-distortion and distortionless ones. The distortionless technique, such as partial transmit sequence, will not influence the system performance so that it is good for higher-level modulation styles. However, the PAPR reduction performance of distortionless technique is not as good as pre-distortion one. In current pre-distortion techniques, peak cancellation has been proved to be efficient and straightforward, in which a series of band-limited window functions are generated to reduce the PAPR, but with increased complexity from inefficient procedures of peak detection and recalculation.

For combating the problem of high complexity of traditional peak cancellation, in this report, a novel low-complexity peak cancellation technique is proposed for an efficient PAPR control.

2.2.2. Possible solutions

In OFDM system with K subcarriers and time-domain oversampling factor J , the modulated data X_k in the k th subcarrier is transformed by inverse fast Fourier transform (IFFT) to get the time-domain OFDM symbol

$$s(n) = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} X'_k e^{j2\pi \frac{kn}{N}}, \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$$

where $N = JK$ and X'_k is the element of data vector $\mathbf{X}' = [X'_0 \ X'_1 \ \dots \ X'_{N-1}]^T$ after $(J-1)K$ zeros is inserted in the middle of the data vector $\mathbf{X} = [X_0 \ X_1 \ \dots \ X_{K-1}]^T$. Therefore, the corresponding PAPR calculated using the J times oversampled time-domain signal samples is given by

$$PAPR = 10 \log \frac{\max_{0 \leq n \leq N-1} \{|s(n)|^2\}}{E\{|s(n)|^2\}},$$

where $\max\{\square\}$ and $E\{\square\}$ denotes the maximum and expectation respectively.

Figure 2.2. Block diagram of the conventional peak cancellation scheme

For PAPR reduction, peak cancellation is adopted for peak detection and cancellation. As shown in Fig. 8.1, the undesired peaks are firstly found out through the block of comparison and detection. Secondly, a serial of weighted coefficients according to each peaks are calculated. Finally, suppression function is generated based on the coefficient for PAPR reduction. In this case, peaks over thresholds can be reduced from the original signal. However, since the peaks are cancelled separately, a serial of cancellations to successive peaks may cause over-cancellation or lack-cancellation due to the inter-cancellation of the suppression functions. As shown in Fig. 8.2, the cancellation for over-threshold signal samples causes excessive attenuation which results in performance degradation of PAPR and BER. Otherwise, although excessive attenuation is avoided for iterative peak cancellation, the processing of peak detection, successive peaks searching and new weighted value calculation results in an increase in computation.

Figure 2.3. the inter-cancellation in case of successive peaks

To improve the PAPR with reduced complexity, this invention proposes a novel peak cancellation method. It uses a joint processing of threshold comparison and peak detection for over-threshold peaks which are then reduced by serial cancellations. Furthermore, its selective serial cancellations for over-threshold peaks avoid redundancy of detection and excessive attenuation.

Figure 2.4. The block diagram of the proposed invention

As shown in Fig. 8. 3, the proposed invention firstly combines comparison between signal amplitude and threshold with peak detection in sample index order. When the sample exceeding the threshold is on the rising edge of signal, comparison happens between current sample and its next sample until the first sample on the falling edge appears. Then, one cancellation for the peak m_i is implemented by a weighted window function, which is the cancellation function in Fig. 8.4. After cancelling one over-threshold peak, the next several samples could be skipped to reduce complexity according to the correlation of oversampled signal. As shown in Fig. 4, when the peak in peak index n_5 suppressed, C_R samples could be avoided comparison, for example, the first next sample is skipped in the case of $C_R = 1$. In this invention, $C_R \in \{1, \dots, J\}$ is referred as correlation distance. Repeating the procedure above until to the maximum iteration value N .

Figure2.5. The implementation of the proposed invention

As illustrated above, the proposed invention has less complexity, since it combines two steps, which are threshold comparison and peak detection, and the serial cancellation does not require recalculating weighted coefficients. Furthermore, the proposed invention detects the peaks based on three adjacent over-threshold samples for precise peak detection so that excessive attenuation is mitigated with the enhanced BER performance.

2.2.3. Objective

The proposed scheme can achieve much lower computational complexity and better BER performance than the traditional peak cancellation scheme. In addition, the proposed scheme offers a promising PAPR reduction performance, so that it is better for the transmission signals with higher power efficiency in eMBB and mMTC environments. Therefore it is suggested to study above solution in future release, and standardize necessary information exchanging between Uu link.

2.3 D2D Assisted MU-MIMO Precoding

2.3.1. Justification

Multi-user multiple-input multiple-output (MU-MIMO) has been adopted as a key enabling technique to achieve the capacity demand in 4G wireless networks. However, there are still some problems existing in the frequency division duplex (FDD) MU-MIMO system, such as the channel quality indicator (CQI) mismatch problem, large uplink feedback, low pairing probability of MU communication. In this report, we exploit a MU-MIMO scheme in FDD assisted by device-to-device (D2D) technique to enhance the conventional LTE network. The proposed scheme could not only solve the above problems in conventional MU-MIMO systems, but also achieve significant performance improvement than conventional MU-MIMO schemes. Since the user pairing process is done at the user side, the feedback of the proposed scheme is reduced dramatically compared with the conventional scheme. Simulation results show that the proposed D2D assisted MU-MIMO scheme has clear superiority in terms of throughput over conventional MU-MIMO scheme in LTE networks. Because with D2D assisted MU-MIMO, the proposed scheme tackles the CQI mismatch problem and increases the multi-user pairing probability to enhance the overall throughput.

2.3.2. Possible solutions

The conventional MU-MIMO system in FDD mode is shown in Fig. 1. Consider a MU-MIMO system where N_T antennas are equipped at eNB and N_R antennas are equipped at each UE. Householder codebooks are generated off line both at the eNB and each UE. Each UE feeds back the vector index PMI from the codebook and its corresponding CQI to the eNB. The eNB implements user scheduling and select precoding matrix from the codebook. There are totally X users to be scheduled and K users to be transmitted according to the feedback channel information and the scheduling criterion, then the scheduled UEs will be precoded by the precoding matrix before transmission. The channel matrix for the k -th UE is presented as

$$\mathbf{H}_k = \begin{bmatrix} h_{1,1} & \cdots & h_{1,M} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ h_{N,1} & \cdots & h_{N,M} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

Where $h_{i,j}$ denotes the channel impulse response coupling the j -th transmitter to the i -th receiver element. The amplitude of $h_{i,j}$ obeys independent and identically Rayleigh-distribution.

For rank-1 FDD MU-MIMO scheme, the precoding algorithm is represented as below:

Step 1 Each UE feeds back a maximum rank-1 CQI to eNB through uplink, which can be defined as

$$\text{CQI}_k = \max_{\mathbf{e}_m \in \mathbf{C}} \frac{\|\mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{e}_m\|}{\sigma^2}, \quad (2)$$

Where \mathbf{e}_m denotes the m -th codebook vector of Householder rank-1 codebook, and \mathbf{C} is the rank-1 Householder codebook.

Step 2 eNB predicts the CQI of paired UE on the basis of rank-1 CQI fed back by UEs. Consider user l and user k are paired successfully, then the predicted $\text{CQI}_{k,predict}$ for the k -th user under MU communication is shown as

$$\text{CQI}_{k,predict} = \frac{\text{CQI}_k / (2n) \times \beta_{11}^2 / \|\mathbf{F}_k\|^2}{1 + \text{CQI}_k / (2n) \times \beta_{12}^2 / \|\mathbf{F}_l\|^2}, \quad (3)$$

$\text{CQI}_{l,predict}$ has similar formulation as $\text{CQI}_{k,predict}$, where user k is regarded as an interference.

$\beta_{i,j} = ((\mathbf{V}'\mathbf{V})(\mathbf{V}'\mathbf{V} + \rho\mathbf{I})^{-1})_{i,j}$, and $\mathbf{V}^H = [\mathbf{e}_k, \mathbf{e}_l]$, \mathbf{e}_k and \mathbf{e}_l are the precoding vector fed back by k -th and l -th user, ρ is taken as the value of SNR. The calculation of $\text{CQI}_{k,predict}$ and $\text{CQI}_{l,predict}$ are implemented when $\mathbf{e}_k \neq \mathbf{e}_l$. If $\mathbf{e}_k = \mathbf{e}_l$, the pairing process fails, user l and user k can not perform the MU communication. Where $\mathbf{F} = [\mathbf{F}_k, \mathbf{F}_l] = \mathbf{V}^H (\mathbf{V}\mathbf{V}^H + \rho\mathbf{I})^{-1}$, \mathbf{F}_k and \mathbf{F}_l are the precoding vector for user k and user l respectively when they are paired. The parameter n is an empirical value.

Step 3 eNB operates the user scheduling and communication mode selection based on the rank-1 CQI and $\text{CQI}_{k,predict}$,

$\text{CQI}_{l,predict}$. The eNB will select the user pair with the maximum $\text{CQI}_{MU,predict}$, where

$$\begin{aligned} \text{CQI}_{MU,predict} &= \log_2(1 + \text{CQI}_{k,predict}) \\ &+ \log_2(1 + \text{CQI}_{l,predict}), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$k, l = 1, 2, \dots, K \quad k \neq l$$

If the $\text{CQI}_{MU,predict} > \log_2(1 + \text{CQI}_{k,predict})$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$, the eNB will launch MU-MIMO precoding.

Otherwise, the SU-MIMO precoding begins.

If user k and user l is the optimal user pair, the received signal at the k -th UE can be represented as

$$\mathbf{y}_k = \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{W} \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{n}_k, k = 1, \dots, K, \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{s} = [p_k s_k \quad p_l s_l], \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{F}_k \quad \mathbf{F}_l]. \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{y}_k denotes the received signal of user k , p_k is the transmitted signal power of the k -th data stream, and the additive noise \mathbf{n}_k obeys distribution $CN(0, N_0)$. The channel matrix at UE side for the k -th user after precoding is

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}} = \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{W}. \quad (8)$$

The linear MMSE decoding vector for the k -th user $\tilde{\mathbf{G}}_k$ correspondingly is shown as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{G}}_k = \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^H (\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_k \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_k^H + \frac{2N_0}{P_0} \mathbf{I}_M)^{-1}, \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{I}_M denotes the $M \times M$ identity matrix and P_0 is the transmitted power of all data streams. In order to analyze the system simply and efficiently, we consider equal power allocation in this report. The equivalent channel matrix of user k after precoding is

$$\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k = \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{F}_k. \quad (10)$$

The SINR for the k -th user with the linear detection is

$$\text{SINR}_k = \frac{p_k |\tilde{\mathbf{G}}_k \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{F}_k|^2}{p_l |\tilde{\mathbf{G}}_k \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{F}_l|^2 + \|\mathbf{G}_k\|_2^2 N_0}. \quad (11)$$

The capacity of the MU-MIMO system can be represented as

$$C_{MU} = \log_2(1 + \text{SINR}_k) + \log_2(1 + \text{SINR}_l). \quad (12)$$

Figure 2.6. The system model of conventional MU-MIMO

In the conventional rank-1 FDD MU-MIMO system, the user is usually unaware of the multi-user interference. Thus, the UEs feeds back an ideal non-interfering rank-1 CQI/PMI through the uplink. Then the eNB predicts the rank-2 CQI for MU communication based on some precoding algorithm such as zero forcing. Although we can reduce the gap between an practical value and the predicted value of CQI by some advanced algorithms, the predicted value is still inaccurate, that would cause CQI mismatch problem. To cope with the above problems, the D2D technique is introduced in FDD MU-MIMO scenario.

The details of the D2D assisted rank-1 FDD MU-MIMO system is as follows

Step 1 Each user estimates the channel matrix \mathbf{H}_k according to the downlink CSI-RS respectively.

Step 2 Each UE calculates the channel capacity value C_k and the optimal precoding vector and its corresponding

index PMI based on \mathbf{H}_k as

$$C_k = \log_2 \left| \mathbf{I} + \frac{1}{N_T N_0} \mathbf{H}_k^H \mathbf{H}_k \right|, \quad (13)$$

Where \mathbf{I} denotes the identity matrix. N_T is the number of transmit antennas, and N_0 is the noise power that obeys $\mathbf{CN} \sim (0,1)$.

Step 3 Each UE calculates the optimal precoding vector according to rank-1 codebook. The k -th user's CQI is calculated as

$$\text{CQI}_k = \max_{\mathbf{e}_m \in \mathbf{C}} \frac{\|\mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{e}_m\|}{N_0}, \quad (14)$$

PMI_k is the corresponding index of the best precoding vector for user k . \mathbf{C} has been defined in equation (2).

Step 4 Each UE broadcasts the channel capacity $C_k, k \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$ and the optimal codebook index $\text{PMI}_k, k \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$ respectively via the D2D link.

Step 5 Based on the information from other UEs and each UE's local channel information, user k will calculate the achievable throughput when combining with user p to form a MU-MIMO pair. The achievable MU-MIMO throughput is expressed as

$$C_{k,p} = (C_k + C_p) \times (1 - |\mathbf{e}_k \mathbf{e}_p^H|), \quad (15)$$

Where \mathbf{e}_k is the precoding vector corresponding to the PMI fed back by the k -th UE, \mathbf{e}_p is the precoding vector corresponding to the PMI fed back by the p -th UE. Each user traverses all possible combinations $C_{k,p}$ to get the set of the approximate sum capacity value $\{C_G\}$. If the set of the approximate sum capacity value $\{C_G\}$ is empty, which indicates that all the UE's codebook index are conflicting and the user pairing fails. Therefore, only the SU communication is performed with the criterion of maximum capacity. If not, turn to step 6.

Step 6 Take a user pair which has the maximum sum capacity value as a optimal pair, denoted as (i, j) . We have

$$(i, j) = \arg \max_{k,p \in \{1,2,\dots,K\}} C_{k,p}. \quad (16)$$

Thus, the i -th UE and the j -th UE are optimal paired UEs. If the UE k is not in the optimal pair (i, j) , this UE enters into a silent state. The UE i in the optimal pair feeds back information SINR_i to eNB as (user j is regarded as an interference)

$$\text{SINR}_i = \frac{p_i |\mathbf{G}_i \mathbf{H}_i \mathbf{F}_i|^2}{p_j |\mathbf{G}_i \mathbf{H}_i \mathbf{F}_j|^2 + \|\mathbf{G}_i\|_2^2 N_0}, \quad (17)$$

Where \mathbf{G}_i denotes the detection matrix, p_i is the transmit power of the i -th user, \mathbf{F}_i is the precoding matrix of user i , which is obtained by zero forcing the codebook vector of user i and user j , it can be presented as

$$\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{F}_i \mathbf{F}_j] = \mathbf{V} (\mathbf{V}^H + \rho \mathbf{I})^{-1}, \quad (18)$$

Where $\mathbf{V}^H = [\mathbf{e}_i \mathbf{e}_j]$, and ρ is a positive number that is generally perceived as the value of SNR, $\mathbf{e}_i, \mathbf{e}_j$ are

the vectors reconstructed from rank-1 Householder codebook by PMI_i and PMI_j . Where $p_i |\mathbf{G}_i \mathbf{H}_i \mathbf{F}_i|^2$

represents the power of useful data, and $p_j |\mathbf{G}_i \mathbf{H}_i \mathbf{F}_j|^2$ represents the power of interfering data, $\|\mathbf{G}_i\|_2^2 N_0$ represents the noise power after the equalization in receiver end. P_0 denotes the transmit power of all data stream, which meets the following total power constraint.

$$p_i + p_j = P_0. \quad (19)$$

To simplify the analysis, we assume that the system allocates power equally. When using linear minimum mean square error (MMSE) detection in the receiver end, we have

$$\mathbf{G}_i = \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_i^H (\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_i \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_i^H + \frac{2N_0}{P_0} \mathbf{I}_N)^{-1}, \quad (20)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_i = \mathbf{H}_i \mathbf{F}_i, \quad (21)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_i = \mathbf{H}_i [\mathbf{F}_i \mathbf{F}_j], \quad (22)$$

Where $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_i$ is the equivalent channel matrix of the i -th user. User j in the optimal pair can also calculate SINR_j in a similar way (user i is regarded as an interference).

Step 7 User i and user j in the optimal pair select the CQI_i and CQI_j according to SINR_i and SINR_j in the UE side, then feed back CQI_i , CQI_j , SINR_i , SINR_j respectively via uplink to eNB.

Step 8 eNB do MU-MIMO precoding according to feedback PMI indexes for user i and user j . The precoding matrix \mathbf{W} is confirmed according to the PMI fed back from the optimal pair. Where $\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{F}_i \mathbf{F}_j] = \mathbf{V} (\mathbf{V} \mathbf{V}^H + \rho \mathbf{I})^{-1}$, and $\mathbf{V}^H = [\mathbf{e}_i \mathbf{e}_j]$. Data is transmitted to each UE from eNB since then.

2.3.3. Objective

When the SNR is higher than 5dB, the proposed scheme achieved significant throughput gain, which outperforms Rank-1 method. This is because with the accurate SINR, the UE side can calculate the best CQI for each paired UEs. Furthermore, this also lies in the appropriate communication mode of UEs, for UEs choose SU communication in the low SNR region, and UE pairs select MU communication in the high SNR region.

The proposed method can be used in downlink mulita-user environment with the aid of D2D, for enhancing the transmission performance while consuming lower feedback amount. Therefore, it is suggested to study above solution in future 3GPP release, and standardize necessary information exchanging between the D2D and Uu link.

2.4 Hybrid CP OFDM

2.4.1. Justification

There is a strong demand for wireless multimedia and interactive Internet services, which is pushing intensive research efforts to develop more efficient communication systems. The judgment criterions of the performance of the system are the spectrum efficiency and the power efficiency.

As is well-known, the orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM), which is a special form of multicarrier, has been widely adopted in many broadband mobile communications owing to its inherent robustness against the inter-symbol interference (ISI). In OFDM, for overcoming the problem that the wideband channels are sensitive to frequency selective fading, the entire channel is divided into a series of narrowband channels experiencing flat fading, which are transmitted in parallel to maintain high-data-rate transmission and, at the same time, to increase the symbol duration to combat ISI. And OFDM introduce the cyclic prefix, which is a periodic extension of the last part of the symbol, to eliminate the inter-carrier interference (ICI) and the inter-symbol interference (ISI), the length of which is supposed to be longer than the channel impulse response (CIR). Although the cyclic prefix introduced by OFDM is useful to mitigate ISI and ICI, this redundancy however results in decrease of the number of channel uses available for signal transmission, which violate the judgment criterion to exploit a more efficient communication system.

For saving the spectrum and meeting the target BER, this section proposes a hybrid CP-OFDM scheme, by changing the conventional approach to add the cyclic prefix that it is used in the front of every frame symbol vectors into the more spectrum-saving method that it is placed only on the front of even frame symbol vectors. Firstly, in the proposed scheme, the half of the spectrum which has been used to carry the cyclic prefix can be saved to transmit useful data. Secondly, the scheme is beneficial to reduce the latency of the system. Thirdly, the similar bit error rate with the conventional OFDM system also is the main competitive advantage.

2.4.2. Possible solutions

Figure 2.7. the frame model of the Hybrid CP OFDM symbol

As can be seen in Fig. 7.1, the cyclic prefix is only inserted in front of even frame symbol vectors that improved the spectral efficiency with respect to the conventional OFDM system before the time domain signals pass through the multipath channel.

OFDM symbols can be expressed as:

$$\text{Time-domain even symbol: } x_{2i}(n) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} X_{2i}(k) e^{j2\pi \frac{k}{N}n} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Time-domain odd symbol: } x_{2i-1}(n) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} X_{2i-1}(k) e^{j2\pi \frac{k}{N}n} \quad (2)$$

where $X_{2i}(k)$ denotes the frequency domain data of the $2i$ -th OFDM symbol, which is independent identically distributed.

The time domain signals (the length of the even frame symbol is $N + N_g$ and the length of the odd frame symbol is N) to be send is as follows:

$$s_{2i} = [x_{2i}(N - N_g), x_{2i}(N - N_g + 1), \dots, x_{2i}(N - 1), x_{2i}(0), \dots, x_{2i}(N - 1)] \quad (3)$$

$$s_{2i-1} = [x_{2i-1}(0), x_{2i-1}(1), \dots, x_{2i-1}(N - 1)] \quad (4)$$

where N is the length of the OFDM symbol, N_g is the length of the cyclic prefix.

Assuming that the synchronization is perfect and perfect channel state information (CSI) is known in the receiver, the received time-domain signal which is obtained by that the transmitted time domain signals go through the multipath channel. The received time domain signals (the length of the received even frame symbol is $N + N_g$ and the length of the received Odd frame symbol is N) can be shown as follows:

$$\text{Time-domain even symbol: } r_{2i} = \bar{r}_{2i} + I^{(2i-1 \rightarrow 2i)} + w_{2i} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Time-domain odd symbol: } r_{2i-1} = \bar{r}_{2i-1} + I^{(2i-2 \rightarrow 2i-1)} + w_{2i-1} \quad (6)$$

where $h_{2i} = [h_{2i}(0), h_{2i}(1), \dots, h_{2i}(L - 1)]$ denotes the impulse response sequence of the multipath channel of the $2i$ -th frame. w_{2i} denotes the additive Gaussian White noise of the $2i$ -th frame. $I^{(k_1 \rightarrow k_2)}$ denotes the interference of the k_1 -th frame to k_2 -th frame. The bottom of Fig. 1 shows the receiver frame symbol model.

$\bar{r}_{2i} = [\Lambda_{2i}(0), \Lambda_{2i}(1), \dots, \Lambda_{2i}(N + N_g - 1)]$ denotes the useful date of the $2i$ -th received symbol.

$\bar{r}_{2i-1} = [\Lambda_{2i-1}(0), \Lambda_{2i-1}(1), \dots, \Lambda_{2i-1}(N - 1)]$ denotes the useful date of the $(2i - 1)$ -th received symbol

The major challenge for high-speed and correct information transmission is inter-symbol interference (ISI) due to the time-dispersive nature of the terrestrial radio channel . The following formulas show how the ISI generates.

$$\Lambda_{2i} = s_{2i} * h_{2i} = [\Lambda_{2i}(0), \Lambda_{2i}(1), \dots, \Lambda_{2i}(N + N_g + L - 1)]_{1 \times (N + N_g + L)} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I^{(2i \rightarrow 2i+1)} &= [\Lambda_{2i}(N + N_g), \dots, \Lambda_{2i}(N + N_g + L - 1), 0, \dots, 0]_{1 \times N} \\
 \Lambda_{2i-1} &= s_{2i-1} * h_{2i-1} = [\Lambda_{2i-1}(0), \Lambda_{2i-1}(1), \dots, \Lambda_{2i-1}(N + L - 1)]_{1 \times (N+L)} \\
 I^{(2i-1 \rightarrow 2i)} &= [\Lambda_{2i-1}(N), \dots, \Lambda_{2i-1}(N + L - 1), 0, \dots, 0]_{1 \times (N+N_g)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

In this case, we can reconstruct ISI and restoring the signals by Fig.7.2

Figure 2.8 The block diagram of the receiver.

2.4.3. Objective

In this report, we proposed a novel HP-OFDM system, in which the cyclic prefix is only inserted in front of half of the OFDM symbols. Therefore, the spectral efficiency is effectively improved by saving the overhead of CP by 50% compared to traditional OFDM. The proposed HP-OFDM can be utilized in eMBB and mMTC environments as a candidate to current OFDM and multiple access environments with enhanced spectral efficiency and reduced latency.

2.5 High Speed Train Solution

2.5.1. Justification

The mobile communication has become an information infrastructure connecting human society, after more than 30 years of explosive development. Motivated by mobile internet and internet of things, the next generation mobile network needs to provide diversified services and satisfy extremely user experience. Seamless wide-area coverage, high- capacity hot-spot, low-latency high-reliability and low-power massive-connection are the four typical technical scenarios that derived from the main application scenarios and service requirements. The seamless wide-area coverage is the basic scenario. The main challenge for 5G is to provide more than 100Mbps user experienced data rate with guaranteed service continuity anytime and anywhere, regardless of static state or high-speed moving, and coverage center or coverage edge.

The high Speed Train (HST) is an important yet extremely challenging scenario for future 5G wireless communication systems. In this deployment scenario, dedicated linear deployment along railway line and the deployments including SFN scenarios captured in Section 6.2 of 3GPP TR 36.878 are considered, and passenger UEs are located in train carriages. For the passenger UEs, if the antenna of relay node for eNB-to-Relay is located at top of

one carriage of the train, the antenna of relay node for Relay-to-UE could be distributed to all carriages. This is a very convenient solution for deploying. Besides, the direct communications for eNB-to-UE should also be considered.

For the transmission scheme, transmit diversity is widely used in this scenario, e.g. space frequency/time block code (SFBC/STBC), which is originally designed to provide better coverage performance. But in HST scenario, passengers are densely distributed, and the service activation ratio is expected to be even higher than those in the office scenario. These diversity schemes suffer from unsatisfactory spectrum efficiency (SE). Besides, more RSs are needed in order to resist the fast channel variance that lead to larger overhead, which further sacrifice the system SE. Therefore it is necessary to investigate new transmission schemes and its related procedures for improving passenger user experience, system SE and critical train communication reliability with very high mobility.

2.5.2. Possible solutions

The possible solutions and enhancements can be considered from aspects of physical layer, handover procedure, coverage improvement, capacity improvement and energy efficiency, as Table 2.1. See [3] for more details.

Table 2.1 Key Technologies and Potential Solutions on high speed enhancement

Physical layer	Handover procedure	Coverage improvement	Capacity improvement	High Energy Efficient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Numerology Design - Channel Estimation and DM-RS Design - Waveform PRACH Enhancement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UE Mobility Identity-based Handover Solution - Power Adjustment assisted Handover 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time-domain power allocation for enhancing near-far coverage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fixed Beam Direction based Transmission - Location-aided MIMO Transmission - Space-Time-Coded Adaptive Spatial Modulation for HSR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Train Arrival Information based Energy Utilization Control

2.5.3. Objective

Agreements and observations in Rel-15 study shall be the starting point. The detailed objectives are to study the following:

1. New waveforms for HSR to accommodate fast channel variation:
 - Transmitter side signal processing schemes
 - Receiver side signal processing schemes
 - The study should take real channel estimation into account

2. MIMO to achieve high spectrum efficiency for HSR, e.g. based on various channel information, and location/mobility trajectory.:
 - Multi-antenna schemes, including new transmission schemes for DL and UL, open loop / semi-open loop / closed loop, MIMO transmission between gNB and mobile relay / passengers UEs.
 - CSI acquisition and feedback: CSI framework, CSI feedback and etc.
 - Beam management: efficient beam tracking, beam switch and etc.
3. Related procedures to the transmission scheme
 - Fast initial access and link adaptation
 - Robust handover procedure
4. Enhanced control & scheduling design
5. Link and system level performance evaluation

3. Support of mMTC scenario

A new type multiple access algorithm named real domain OFDM is suggested for mMTC scenario to satisfy the connection density key capability.

3.1 real domain OFDM

3.1.1. Justification

In fifth generation (5G), mMTC services are expected to play an essential role. Currently, the cellular systems have been mainly designed and optimized to serve traffic from human-to-human (H2H) communications, which are generally characterized by bursts of data during active periods with a higher demand on downlink. However, major MTC services have very different traffic characteristics: usually small and infrequent data generated from a mass of MTC devices imposing a higher traffic volume on uplink. Therefore, the main challenge in mMTC is to support scalable and efficient connectivity for a massive number of devices sending very short packets. The connection density becomes one of the most important and challenging key performance indicators (KPIs). In fact, to provide satisfactory solutions to mMTC services, multiple technologies in a wide range should be used together, including random access, NOMA and waveform. On the other hand, the peak-to-average-power-ratio (PAPR) is also a major optimization goal for mMTC services since lower PAPR leads to long battery life, high power amplification efficiency, wide coverage and possible cost reduction. This makes the waveform with low PAPR very attractive for mMTC services.

3.1.2. Possible solutions

Currently, OFDM-based waveforms have been accepted in NR eMBB for their high spectral efficiency with reasonable complexity. This property comes from the minimized subcarrier spacing together with inter-subcarrier orthogonality in the complex domain. According to many literatures [4][5][6], the subcarrier spacing of OFDM can be halved to keep orthogonality only in the real domain. By doing so, the resource element (RE) density can be doubled. This will benefit the mMTC service which has an optimization goal of connection density. This halved subcarrier spacing waveform is called real domain OFDM (r-OFDM) in this study.

The signal of K-subcarrier conventional OFDM can be expressed as:

$$s_{OFDM}(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{T}} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} a_k \cdot e^{\frac{j2\pi kt}{T}} \quad (0 < t < T)$$

where a_k could be a complex number modulated on k-th subcarrier .

Then r-OFDM is obtained by halving the subcarrier spacing and transmitting real-valued data. Given the same total bandwidth and symbol duration time, r-OFDM can accommodate $2K$ subcarriers which can be formulated as:

$$s_{r-OFDM}(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{T}} \sum_{k=0}^{2K-1} b_k \cdot e^{\frac{j2\pi kt}{2T}} \quad (0 < t < T)$$

where b_k is k-th subcarrier data and real-valued. The received signal in AWGN is:

$$y_{r-OFDM}(t) = s_{r-OFDM}(t) + n(t)$$

where $n(t)$ is additive white Gaussian noise. The k-th subcarrier data can be detected by:

$$\hat{b}_k = \text{real} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{T}} \int_0^T y_{r-OFDM}(t) \cdot e^{-\frac{j2\pi kt}{2T}} dt \right) = b_k + n_k$$

where n_k is the noise part after k-th de-filter.

In this way, the resource element (RE) density of the waveform is doubled over that of the OFDM as shown in figure 2.9.

Figure 2.9. Resource grid of OFDM (left) and r-OFDM (right)

Note that it is similar to but actually very different from the concept of flexible numerology of OFDM, in which flexible symbol duration or subcarrier spacing can be achieved as long as the product of them is one. For example, if the subcarrier spacing is halved, the symbol duration has to be doubled for the flexible numerology of OFDM. Therefore, there is no spectral efficiency gain.

Similar to DFT-s-OFDM in LTE uplink, in order to reduce PAPR, a discrete cosine transform (DCT) matrix based pre-coding/spreading is performed before r-OFDM modulation at the transmitter, as shown in figure 2.10.

Figure 2.10. Transmitter of DCT-r-OFDM

The DCT was chosen instead of DFT for two reasons. The first one is that DCT is a real domain transform. If the input of the DCT is real valued, the output will be real valued too. So all the precoded data will be kept in the real domain. And the second reason is that the DCT has the same subcarrier spacing as that of r-OFDM, which is halved than that of OFDM. In addition, the DCT is a wellknown method to reduce PAPR of multicarrier systems [2] and [7]-[9] due to its energy compaction property [5] [6]. It is also found that, in terms of PAPR reduction, DCT is better than DFT [2].

Instead of high spectral efficiency and peak data rate, which are the main optimization goals of Human-type communication (HTC) services, the mMTC services, which only need very low data rate, more focus on high connection density, wide coverage, low cost and low complexity. To achieve these, the low order modulation could be a good choice. For low order modulation such as BPSK, DCT-r-OFDM can provide doubled subcarriers over DFT-s-OFDM in the same bandwidth. Consequently, it potentially supports doubled connection density. On the other hand, PAPR is also one main optimization goal of mMTC since low PAPR can provide wider coverage, save power consumption and allow small-size devices. According to the theoretical analysis and simulation results in [6], DCT-r-OFDM can have the lower PAPR than DFT-s-OFDM. In conclusion, due to the doubled connection density in potential and lower PAPR, DCT-r-OFDM can be a good candidate waveform to replace the DFT-s-OFDM for mMTC services.

3.1.3. Objective

- 1) Expect output for this work/feature.

It is expected to propose a new waveform termed DCT-r-OFDM to replace the OFDM or DCT-s-OFDM for the uplink of mMTC services due to its potential doubled connect density and lower PAPR.

- 2) Investigation methodology.

For real domain modulation schemes such as BPSK, DCT-r-OFDM can have doubled spectral efficiency over that of DFT-s-OFDM due to its halved subcarrier spacing. Link level simulations should be used to verify the performance of DCT-r-OFDM with BPSK and DFT-s-OFDM is used as the baseline for comparison in terms of the block error rate (BLER), bandwidth and PAPR.

- 3) Potential impact to specification.

New waveform, including the new resource grid description, for the uplink of mMTC services to enhance the connection density and reduce the PAPR. Possible new DMRS design.

4. New Features

In this chapter, positioning based on NR of 5G is proposed as a new feature in next 3GPP release. And NOMA, which has been studied in Rel-15, is expected to be standardized in Rel-16.

4.1 NR Positioning

4.1.1. Justification

UE positioning has been a key feature in 3GPP due to the immense commercial applications and the regulatory positioning requirements. For 3G/4G systems, 3GPP has developed the architecture, the interfaces, the protocols, the procedures, and a number of methods for supporting UE positioning operations. 3GPP is currently working on 5G new radio (NR) system in full speed, which will introduce a new set of designs with advanced features. This provides a unique opportunity to start working on new 5G NR positioning technologies, so that the designs for 5G NR positioning and the designs for mobile radio data communication can be seamlessly integrated together.

5G will post more stringent requirements on NR positioning than 3G/4G as follows:

- High accuracy. In the order of sub-meters for high performance real-time applications.
- Reliability and availability. High reliability for mission critical applications with high availability.
- Time latency. Very short time to first fix (TTFF) for time critical applications, e.g., for ultra low latency ultra-reliable low latency communications (URLLC) services.
- Coverage. Indoor and Outdoor in various deployment scenarios.
- Horizontal and vertical positioning.
- Scalability. Number of UEs in orders-of-magnitude increase from current 3G/4G network.
- Power Consumption. Extremely low power consumption for some applications, e.g., mMTC services.
- Simplified network architecture, interface and protocols.

For example, according to 3GPP TS 22.261, the 5G system will support the use of 3GPP and non-3GPP technologies to achieve higher-accuracy positioning of 0.5m with time to first fix (TTFF) of 500ms and with availability of 99.99%. Thus, it is essential to start investigating efficient and high performance NR positioning for supporting these requirements.

4.1.2. Possible solutions

Developing high performance NR positioning system requires the investigation of the effective solutions in NR positioning architecture, network interfaces, positioning protocols, positioning procedures, and positioning methods.

NR Positioning Architecture and Network Interfaces

It is essential to implement efficient positioning architecture to support challenging NR positioning requirements in order to support unprecedented number of UEs, wider variety of use cases (highly accurate and reliable UE position

information with very short latency, extremely low power consumptions for mMTC applications, diverse deployment scenarios (standalone/non-standalone, licensed/unlicensed bands, dense-urban/urban/suburban/rural areas, etc.), as well as smooth integration with existing 3G/4G and other RAT positioning systems. NR network will re-define and also develop new network entities and network interfaces for supporting the NR positioning architecture.

NR Positioning Protocols and Positioning Procedures

E-UTRAN positioning is supported in both control-plane and user-plane protocols. For example, LTE Positioning Protocol (LPP) carrying information between the UE and the E-SMLC, LTE Positioning Protocol Annex (LPPa) between the eNode B and the E-UTRAN Serving Mobile Location Center (E-SMLC), S1 Application Protocol carries LPP/LPPa messages over the S1-MME interface, and SLm Application Protocol carries positioning messages between the E-SMLC and the location measurement unit (LMU).

NR positioning protocols can be developed with the consideration of existing E-UTRAN positioning protocols. For example, NR Positioning Protocols should be developed based on LPP/LPPa protocols, since LPP/LPPa protocols were developed with the consideration of forward-compatibility with other RATs to avoid creating new positioning protocols. NR will also define the new RRC protocol with the objective of network functions virtualization (NFV) and network slicing. The transport for NR positioning messages and measurements should be supported with the new RRC protocol. Other application protocols responsible for message transportation between new network entries also need to be investigated.

Positioning procedures are defined as transactions of the positioning protocols. For E-UTRAN network, 3GPP has defined the necessary positioning procedures (e.g., LPP/LPPa/SLmAP procedures) for supporting positioning applications. New positioning procedures will need to be developed for supporting NR location applications based on the new 5G network architecture, interfaces, and protocols.

NR Positioning Methods

UE positioning can be standalone (e.g., GNSS) or network-assisted (e.g., network-assisted GNSS). From 3GPP point of view, the focus has been on the network-assisted positioning methods, although standalone methods are also supported.

Network-assisted positioning has two operating modes: UE-assisted and UE-based. UE position may be estimated based on measurements of downlink reference signals, e.g., the observed time difference of arrival (OTDOA), positioning reference signals (PRS)-based terrestrial beacon systems (TBS); or based on measurements of uplink positioning reference signals, e.g., the uplink difference of arrival (UTDOA), or based on inertial, optical. The NR should enable, and improve if suitable, state-of-art positioning techniques, such as RAN-dependent (E-CID, OTDOA, UTDOA, etc.), RAN-independent (GNSS, Bluetooth, WLAN, Terrestrial Beacon Systems (TBS), inertial measurement unit (IMU), barometers, etc.), and integrated solutions with both RAN-dependent and independent solutions. In addition, potential device to device (D2D) based positioning techniques should be considered.

The NR positioning methods will also exploit large bandwidth and utilization of massive antenna arrays to substantially improve the positioning accuracy. The possibility to use wide signal bandwidth brings new positioning performance bounds for RAN-dependent positioning techniques, e.g., OTDOA, UTDOA. The recent advances in massive antenna systems (massive MIMO) can provide additional information to enable more accurate user location by exploiting spatial and angular domains of propagation channel in combination with time measurements.

4.1.3. Objective

The objective of this study item is to evaluate potential solutions to address NR positioning requirements as defined in TR 38.913 and TS 22.261 while considering E911 requirements by analysing positioning accuracy (including latitude, longitude and altitude), availability, reliability, latency, network synchronization requirements and/or UE/gNB complexity to perform positioning, and taking into account a preference to maximize synergy where possible with existing positioning support for E-UTRAN. This SI covers RAT dependent, RAT independent, and hybrid of those positioning technologies.

1. Evaluation on different positioning technologies

- For RAT dependent technologies,
 - Use the evaluation assumptions and scenarios in TR37.857 as a starting point including:
 - Indoor and outdoor deployment scenarios covering but not limited to Urban and Suburban areas
 - System parameters including operating bands below and above 6GHz
 - User dropping
 - Performance metrics to evaluate vertical and horizontal positioning and the overall positioning accuracy and latency
 - Define additional evaluation assumptions and scenarios, if needed.
 - Evaluate the positioning technologies.

2. Study of potential positioning solutions for RAT dependent technologies and hybrid of those against the objectives in TR 38.913 and TS 22.261.

- For RAT dependent technologies, the study is based on measurement of NR signals for downlink and uplink transmission

3. Study of NR positioning architecture for location services, functional interfaces, protocol and procedures for supporting RAT dependent, RAT independent, and hybrid of RAT dependent and independent positioning technologies including the following:

- Architectures and interfaces to support RAT independent positioning technologies
- Architectural and signalling support (e.g. reuse/extension of LPP/LPPa/RRC vs. new protocol, etc.)

4. Study of the support in standalone (NR only) and mixed LTE-NR deployments

4.2 NOMA

4.2.1. Justification

Similar to LTE, the basic multiple access scheme for NR is orthogonal for both downlink and uplink data transmissions, meaning that time and frequency physical resources of different users are not overlapped. On the other hand, non-orthogonal multiple-access schemes recently gained wide interest, prompting Rel-13 Study Item on downlink

multi-user superposition transmission (MUST) and some initial study in Rel-14 Study Item on NR. The latter was stopped before completion, to concentrate on more urgent features for Rel-15 NR Work Item.

Many non-orthogonal multiple-access schemes are evaluated in the Rel-14 NR study item. For the evaluated scenarios the results show significant benefit of non-orthogonal multiple access in terms of UL link-level sum throughput and overloading capability, as well as system capacity enhancement in terms of supported packet arrival rate at given system outage. The Rel-14 Study Item further identified that NR should at least target UL non-orthogonal multiple access at least for mMTC. Therefore, study on non-orthogonal multiple access shall continue in Rel-15.

For non-orthogonal multiple access, there will be interference between transmissions using overlapping resources. As the system load increases, this non-orthogonal characteristic is more pronounced. To combat the interference between non-orthogonal transmissions, transmitter side schemes such as spreading (linear or non-linear, with or without sparseness) and interleaving are normally employed to improve the performance and ease the burden of advanced receivers.

SIC is considered as the general decoding scheme in power-domain non-orthogonal multiple access. However, the large differences of the paired users in received power level are the key for the good performance of SIC. Indeed, in practical scenario, it is not always possible to guarantee the large differences in power levels for SIC decoding, in particular, when there is asymmetric number between far users and near users. To solve this problem, compute-and-forward receiver is employed for uplink non-orthogonal multiple access to improve the performance of fairness and average outage probability.

Generally speaking, non-orthogonal transmission can be applied to both grant-based and grant-free transmission. The benefits of non-orthogonal multiple access, particularly when enabling grant-free transmission, may encompass a variety of use cases or deployment scenarios, including eMBB, URLLC, mMTC, DL for multi-site transmission etc. In RRC_CONNECTED state, it saves the scheduling request procedure assuming UE is already uplink synchronized. In RRC_INACTIVE state, data can be transmitted even without RACH procedure or with 2-step RACH. The saving of the signalling naturally also saves UE's power consumption, reduces latency and increases system capacity. Non-orthogonal multiple access can benefit both Uu and side link.

4.2.2. Possible solutions

Transmitter side signal processing schemes for non-orthogonal multiple access

- Using the following unified framework of NOMA scheme
 - Cell /user specific bit level interleaver / scrambler
 - Long or short spreading
 - Cell/user specific symbol interleaver/scrambler

Figure 2.11. Transmitter side signal processing schemes

Receivers for non-orthogonal multiple access

Different from the SUD receiver adopted in OMA, MUD receiver is needed in NOMA to distinguish different transmissions using overlapping resources, which holds a higher complexity. Furthermore, the system performance improvement achieved by NOMA heavily relies on the receiver.

For current NOMA schemes, MUD receivers are designed mainly based on ML, SIC, and, MMSE etc. NOMA receivers based on ML can achieve the best performance by jointly detecting the superposed transmissions, but the complexity is high and increases exponentially as the number of superposed transmissions increases. Therefore, some substitute receiver with reduced complexity is designed to approximate ML, i.e., message passing algorithm (MPA). MPA receiver is able to effectively utilize the spreading feature at transmitter side to dramatically reduce receiver complexity but without losing too much performance compared with ML receiver. NOMA receivers based on SIC holds low complexity, which increases linearly as the number of superposed transmissions increases. However, error propagation from previous detection to subsequent operation in SIC leads to performance loss. MMSE is linear detection, which holds lowest complexity but poor performance. It could be combined to SIC receiver to improve performance by enhancing desired signal and weakening interference in received signal. Consequently, each NOMA receiver type holds a certain complexity inherently and the complexity order of different types may change depending on system parameters. As design targets may vary across different working scenarios, NOMA receivers should be carefully evaluated by considering both performance and complexity in each possible working scenarios.

The possible solutions include:

- Advanced receivers beyond MMSE-IRC, e.g., MPA/EPA, MMSE-SIC, MPA-SIC, ESE-PIC, compute-and-forward receiver (Note that compared with SIC receiver, compute-and-forward receiver decode two integer-linear combination and then decode the individual signal.)
- Taking joint consideration of performance, latency, and complexity.

Procedures related to the non-orthogonal multiple access

- Grant-free transmission first;
- Consider both synchronous and asynchronous scenario, where synchronous scenario is with higher priority.

4.2.3. Objective

This study will further progress on the evaluation of non-orthogonal multiple access schemes focusing on uplink, and provide recommendation on the non-orthogonal multiple access scheme(s) to be specified later.

Agreements, observations and evaluation assumption in Rel-14 study shall be the starting point. The detailed objectives are to study the following:

1 non-orthogonal multiple transmission scheme

1.1 Transmitter side signal processing schemes for non-orthogonal multiple access [RAN1]:

- Modulation and symbol level processing, including spreading, repetition, interleaving, new constellation mapping, etc.
- Coded bit level processing including interleaving and/or scrambling, etc.
- Symbol to resource element mapping, sparse or not, etc.
- Demodulation reference signal. Other signal is not excluded.

- 2.1 Receivers for non-orthogonal multiple access: [RAN1, RAN4]
 - MMSE receiver, successive/parallel interference cancellation (SIC/PIC) receiver, joint detection (JD) type receiver, combination of SIC and JD receiver, compute-and-forward receiver or other receivers
 - The study should consider performance, receiver complexity, etc.
- 3.1 Procedures related to the non-orthogonal multiple access [RAN1]
 - UL transmission detection
 - HARQ, including transmission scheme, feedback scheme, and combining scheme
 - Link adaptation MA signature allocation/selection
 - Synchronous and asynchronous operation
 - Adaptation between orthogonal and non-orthogonal multiple access
- 4.1 Link and system level performance evaluation or analysis for non-orthogonal multiple access continued from performance metrics identified from Rel-14. The benchmark for comparison is OFDM contention based multiple access. Realistic modelling of Tx/Rx impairment including potential PAPR issue, channel estimation error, power control accuracy, collision, etc. should be considered. [RAN1]
 - Traffic model and Deployment scenarios of eMBB (small packet), URLLC and mMTC
 - Device power consumption
 - Coverage (link budget)
 - Latency and signalling overhead
 - BLER reliability, capacity and system load
 - Physical abstraction (link-to-system mapping model)

Note: targeting common solution for mMTC, URLLC and eMBB small packet.

5. Efficient network management

Wireless big data based intelligent RAN architecture is proposed to enable more efficient Radio access network management in this chapter.

5.1 Wireless Big Data Driven Intelligent RAN Architecture

5.1.1. Justification

5G networks are more and more characterized by the integration of distributed and centralized computing and storage resources. Potentially, amount of wireless data can be collected from the Core network (CN), Radio Access Network (RAN), users and wireless applications. Thanks to the central unit introduce in 5G and potentially deployed edge computing at the RAN side, these provide the capabilities for the big data analytics at the RAN side. In contrast to the traditional data processing at the RAN, the potential advantages of introducing wireless big data analytics for intelligent RAN can be observed for the following aspects:

1. It could be used to make reliable prediction, such as the user position/trajectory, mobility behaviour and service type predictions, etc. Such predictions can help in stabilizing the wireless connections, making better utilization of the radio resources, as well as proactive network control and even potentially simplifying the signaling procedures.
2. It enables context mining of the potential RAN characteristics, such as the channel environment, user density and distribution, adjacent cell interference, spatial and temporal traffic variation, etc. With the aid of the context information, RAN configurations can be efficiently adapted to the site-specific environment and even to slice/service/user specific control, so as to achieve better user experience and efficient resource utilization.
3. It may enhance the RRM performance with powerful machine learning/deep learning tools compared with the traditional sub-optimal solutions for complex RRM problems, especially with huge amount of optimization variables and features in 5G NR, which is expected to be helpful for alleviating the performance loss due to the ideal modelling and approximation used in the traditional radio resource management (RRM) and link adaptation methods. Traditional works attempt to find the optimal parameters and configuration based on the modelling of the system performance expressions and mathematical formulations of the optimization problems. However, the increasingly complex network makes it extremely hard to directly find the mapping function between the objectives and wide range of variables. Reinforcement learning with neural networks may help to analyze and learn what the proper action is for each current network state. In addition, in practice, impairments such as interference and analog circuit nonlinearities are difficult to be described in a simple and tractable framework. Moreover, these impairments are in flux due to environmental factors. Big data techniques may help to real-time capturing of performance related data and even learn some potential factors not provided by the traditional theoretical modeling. This is expected to close up the gap between the theoretical models and the realistic performance.

All the above reasons indicate that, there is sufficient incentive for introducing wireless big data analytics for intelligent RAN. It is envisioned that significant benefit on wireless resource usage efficiency and user experience can be obtained leveraging the context mining and prediction based on the collected RAN data.

For the 5G core network, the network data analytics (NWDA) is already introduced in the 5Gs-Ph1 to automatically feedback network data analytics to the network. Furthermore, a study item on big data driven network architecture for 5G is already approved in SA2. The study item aims to investigate solutions for a big data driven network architecture with information management across all technical domains for context mining. However, this work focuses on the core network, thus inherently cannot handle some RAN enhancement efficiently due to the interaction overhead and process delay. In addition to the overhead and process delay considerations, it worth noting that most of the RAN enhancement greatly depends on the potential characteristics of the RAN, e.g., the varying channel environment, user density and distribution, adjacent cell interference, radio resource availability, etc. Thus, for RAN enhancement, it is more appropriate to also include the wireless big data analytics at the local RAN side. Core network may potentially provide some useful context information and base modeling.

To support the wireless big data analytics for RAN, it is attractive to introduce a logical big data analytics function in the RAN side, and consider its interface with gNB-CU/gNB-DU and different layers of RAN (e.g. PHY\MAC\RLC\PDCP\RRC) for data/model collection and policy/parameter configuration. The logical big data function can easily support the various use cases by just updating the model and algorithm in the big data function. The operators can also possibly update the model and algorithm in the big data function according to their own use cases by themselves or with the help of vendors. The definition of the logical big data function is also good for the flexible deployment, either in the Cloud-RAN or other computing nodes at the edge of the RAN. Note that the logical big data analytics function in the RAN side is expected to be the RAN matching element to the NWDA in core network.

In 5G RAN phase 1, gNB-CU/gNB-DU architecture to support centralized deployment has been introduced to improve collaboration and pooling gains. Under such centralized deployment, it is expected to deploy gNB-CU with more powerful processing and storage capabilities. And thus, it is natural to host computation and storage intensive functionalities (i.e., CUDA, CU data analytics) in gNB-CU, such as data collections, data storage, data processing (including data model training and distribution of well trained models). In the meanwhile, some relatively less demanding functionalities (i.e., DUDA, DU data analytics) can be placed on gNB-DU, e.g., data report, data models decision making and execution with reception of well trained models from gNB-CUDA.

The SID will focus on architecture, protocol and signaling procedure for the data driven Intelligent RAN enhancement as well as identified relevant use case during the study.

Note that the proposed study item would be an important complementary part to the SA2 study item on data driven Network architecture. Together with the SA2 SID, it completes the whole framework of the big data driven 5G design.

5.1.2. Possible solutions

Currently, study on wireless big data driven intelligent RAN architecture is in an initial stage, and the solution needs more effort. Related information can be found in [10].

5.1.3. Objective

The objective of the study item is to:

- Study and identify the use cases and requirements for wireless *big data driven Intelligent RAN enhancement*
 - Collect the RAN use cases based on the local big data computing for more efficient use of resources and better user experience (e.g., enhancing user experience data rate and average throughput, improving handover performance, shorter access and round trip transmission (RTT) delay, etc);
- Study the wireless data driven intelligent RAN architecture, the interfaces and signalling flows considering both the centralized (i.e., gNB-CU/gNB-DU architecture) and non-centralized (i.e., integrated gNB architecture)
 - How RAN could collect the data required for data driven intelligent RAN enhancement from different RAN layers (e.g., RRC/PDCP/L2 measurement from eNB and UE) and adjacent RAN nodes;
 - How RAN could support the big data analytics and training of local big data model for intelligent RAN enhancement via utilizing the collected RAN data and also the data sent from the core network.

Note: the SA2 study item on big data driven network architecture may provide some useful data and/or basic model for the training of the RAN local big data model.

- How RAN could support the distribution of the well processed data features and trained local big data model to different layers and users for RAN enhancement.

in order to at least support (non-exhaustive list):

- 5G QoS enhancement e.g. QoS model training and prediction, 5G QoS target fulfilment verification and policy for QoS flow-to-DRB mapping and remapping based on QoS model and traffic pattern.

- Customized mobility management per UE, e.g., RAN notification enhancement, handover policy, mobility configuration, e.g., handover threshold, measurement configuration, based on services, UE mobility pattern and propagation environment learning
- RAN slice resource sharing optimization based on the prediction of the traffic and resource usage pattern
- Link adaptation enhancement, e.g., to support machine learning based , rank adaptation, modulation and coding to better match the channel variations.

6. Summary

3GPP is going to release its first version of 5G specification (Rel-15) on June in 2018. As the initial 5G specification, there is still a big gap between Rel-15 and the requirements of IMT-2020 on the performance and supported scenarios. This white paper captured proposals on standardization of 3GPP Rel-16 and beyond from industry, universities and research institutes in 2017, which relate to key capabilities enhancement, supporting new scenario, new features and efficient network operation & maintain. It is expected that some convergence or agreements can be made at the beginning of Rel-16 to promote the efficiency of standardization procedure and the quality of specification. This white paper will provide important information for organizations who are 3GPP members already in following 5G standardization. Inputting to this white paper is also a good chance for organizations who are not 3GPP member yet to take part in the 3GPP 5G standardization progress.

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Abbreviation

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	the Fifth-Generation mobile communications
BER	Bit Error Rate
BS	Base Station
CIR	Channel Impulse Response
CN	Core Network
CP	Cyclic Prefix
CQI	Channel Quality Indicator
D2D	Device to Device
DCT	Discrete Cosine Transform
DL	Downlink
DRX	Discontinuous Reception
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
EPDCCH	Enhanced Physical Downlink Control Channel
E-SMLC	Evolved Serving Mobile Location Center
ETC	Electronic Toll Collection
E-UTRA	Evolved Universal Terrestrial Radio Access
E-UTRAN	Evolved Universal Terrestrial Radio
FDD	Frequency Division Duplex
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
HST	High Speed Train
HTC	Human-type communication
ICI	Inter-Carrier Interference
IFFT	Inverse Fast Fourier transform
IMT-Advanced	International Mobile Telecommunication Advanced
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IoT	Internet of Things

ISI	Inter-Symbol Interference
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LMU	Location Measurement Unit
LPP	LTE Positioning Protocol
LPPa	LTE Positioning Protocol Annex
LTE	Long Term Evolution
MAC	Medium Access Control
MMSE	Minimum Mean Square Error
mMTC	Massive MTC
MU-MIMO	Multiple User Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
MUST	Multi-User Superposition Transmission
NB	Node B
NFV	Network Functions Virtualization
NOMA	Non-orthogonal Frequency Division
NR	New Radio
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division
OTDOA	Observed Time Difference Of Arrival
PAPR	Peak-to-Average Power Ratio
PDCCH	Physical Downlink Control CHannel
PDCP	Packet Data Convergence Protocol
PHY	PHysical Layer
QoS	Quality of Service
RACH	Random Access CHannel
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology
RB	Radio Bearer
RE	Resource Element
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
RLC	Radio Link Control
RRC	Radio Resource Control
SFBC	Space Frequency Block Code
SIC	Successive Interference Cancellation
STBC	Space Time Block Code
TBS	Terrestrial Beacon Systems
TDD	Time Division Duplex
UE	User Equipment
UL	Uplink
URLLC	Ultra Reliability Low Latency Communication
UTDOA	Uplink Time Difference Of Arrival
V2V	Vechile to Vechile

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